

ISic0632

I.Sicily inscription 0632

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2013.10.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Piazza Matteotti

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50739

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175845

EDR 073621

EDCS 15100066

Bibliography

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